

1 Different operationalizations of local research and their associated citation
2 patterns: A study of African publications

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20
21 **Abstract**

22 Local research has gained increasing attention in recent years, with a growing body of literature emphasizing its
23 significance—especially for peripheral communities underrepresented in mainstream scientific discourse.
24 However, despite this growing interest, there remains no clear consensus on how to define local research.
25 Conceptual clarity is essential for conducting consistent and replicable analyses that capture the specific
26 characteristics, contexts, and societal relevance of local research. This need is particularly acute in the Global
27 South, where structural inequalities in visibility and recognition often marginalize regionally focused scholarship.
28 In Africa, for instance, a substantial share of research is published in local or regional journals that are poorly
29 represented in global indexing databases. As bibliometric analyses typically rely on these databases, this exclusion
30 diminishes their perceived relevance. To address this gap, the present study incorporates data from regional and
31 open-access sources to examine citation patterns associated with African local research. It uses multiple
32 conceptualizations of local research to classify publications as either local or non-local depending on the definition
33 used. These classifications are correlated with three citation-based indicators: average citations per publication,
34 time to first citation, and the proportion of uncited publications. Additionally, the study explores the characteristics
35 of citing publications, distinguishing between local and non-local sources as well as domestic and international
36 citations. The findings reveal that citation patterns differ significantly across locality definitions, underscoring the
37 importance of adopting nuanced, context-sensitive approaches to assess and support local research.

38
39 **1. Introduction**

40 Local research has garnered increasing attention in recent years, with a growing body of
41 scientific literature emphasizing its importance—particularly for peripheral communities that
42 are underrepresented in global or mainstream research contexts. Research grounded in local
43 realities is essential for understanding the specific conditions and needs of diverse communities
44 and for designing effective, context-sensitive policies. Yet, limited resources and the imposition
45 of international research agendas often hinder the development of studies addressing local

1 issues that may be considered irrelevant by the broader, predominantly Western, academic
2 community (e.g., Ciarli & Ràfols, 2019; Kumar et al., 2024; Moscona & Sastry, 2022).

3 Despite growing academic interest in local research, there is still no clear consensus on what
4 constitutes it. Recently, Di Césare and Robinson-García (2026) made a valuable contribution
5 to such a shared understanding by creating a multidimensional framework for the conceptual
6 and operational definition of local research. In bibliometric studies, it is important to understand
7 what ‘local’ means in relation to research because choosing one definition over another can
8 significantly affect the outcome of a study, potentially obscuring or minimizing the visibility
9 and relevance of local research outputs. Therefore, according to the authors, it is imperative that
10 bibliometric studies on local research clearly define their conceptual approach and
11 methodological operationalization. This particularly applies to bibliometric studies of the
12 Global South, where structural inequalities in visibility and recognition often relegate
13 regionally focused research to the margins of global scientific discourse—a challenge that is
14 also acute in the African context, where a substantial portion of research is published in local
15 or regional journals with limited representation in major indexing databases (Alonso-Álvarez,
16 2024; Asubiaro & Onaolapo, 2023). Since bibliometric analyses typically rely on these
17 databases (e.g., Confraria & Godinho, 2015; Sooryamoorthy, 2022), the impact of publications
18 excluded from them frequently remains invisible.

19 This bibliometric study used an online collection of peer-reviewed African academic journals
20 to explore the relationship between different operationalizations of local research and its
21 impact, the latter of which was measured by citations. Based on previous studies of the citation-
22 related associations of different approaches to defining local research (see Section 2 for a
23 discussion), it is anticipated that the way in which local research is operationalized in an African
24 collection will influence its associated citation patterns and thus its global visibility. The study
25 is therefore about how the choice of measurement affects potential conclusions in research
26 evaluation. Four objectives guided the study:

- 27 • to operationalize selected definitions of local research for a set of African publications
- 28 • to explore the relationships between the different operationalizations
- 29 • to study the associated citation patterns of the different operationalizations, using three
30 measures: (1) average citations per publication, (2) average years to first citation, and
31 (3) percentage of publications with zero citations
- 32 • to explore the profiles of publications that cite the different operationalizations, focusing
33 on locality status (local vs. non-local) and geographic location (same country vs.
34 different country).

35 The next section (Section 2) presents the different conceptualizations of local research and
36 previous work on the associated citation patterns of each conceptualization of local research.
37 Section 3 presents the approaches used for their bibliometric operationalization, the data
38 sources, and outlines the methodology. Section 4 presents and discusses the results. Finally,
39 Section 5 concludes.

41 **2. Conceptualizing and operationalizing local research**

42 Although precise definitions of local science are scarce, it is largely associated with indigenous
43 knowledge systems by historians and sociologists of science, primarily as a means of
44 contrasting it with international science (Kanhadilok, 2014; Sillitoe, 2007). In his edited book,
45 *Local Science vs. Global Science: Approaches to Indigenous Knowledge in International*
46 *Development*, Sillitoe (2007, p. 3) claims to have resisted “the urge to define global and local
47 science”. However, the outlines of each are clear from the book’s title and content. Local

1 science is characterized as a form of knowledge that is neither unique nor singular, but rather
2 multiple and variable according to the place in which it is developed. It is also grounded in the
3 cultural adaptation of a group to a particular environment. By contrast, international or global
4 science is considered universal and based on established methodologies that are
5 institutionalized and accepted as a knowledge standard. In line with this definition, local science
6 is therefore a form of knowledge that does not follow a precise method, is neither
7 institutionalized nor systematically recorded, and is bound to a particular place. Moreover, the
8 tension between local and global science is not only epistemological, but also political,
9 reflecting broader power asymmetries in the production of knowledge.

10 Local science has also been associated with colonial science, given that it is primarily in the
11 (former) colonies where this type of knowledge is produced, while the metropolises retain control
12 over the “intellectual objectives” of science (Chambers, 1993, p. 609), that is, over what
13 constitutes valid scientific knowledge. Building on this, sociologists of science and decolonial
14 scholars have defended the thesis that all science is local (Chambers, 2020; Quijano, 1992;
15 Harding, 1997; Mignolo, 2018; Turnbull, 1993; Turnbull, 1997). As such, it “may be bounded
16 by tangibles, such as socioeconomic circumstances, legalities, colonizing forces, topographies,
17 and technologies; and by abstractions [and] may be further shaped by such factors as race and
18 gender, ideology, and religious belief” (Chambers & Gillespie, 2000, p. 228). In this sense,
19 ‘local’ simply refers to science developed in a particular place, whether that be a region,
20 country, city or institution. It therefore implicitly or explicitly incorporates the social, cultural,
21 political and economic factors of that place.

22 However, this interpretation does not address specific questions about which scientific outputs
23 can be considered local, other than to include all of them. For example, is an output associated
24 with multiple localities—through the different affiliations of its authors, the different
25 geographic foci of the research, or the different intended audiences—also local? For
26 sociologists of science, it might well be, insofar as it incorporates the local contexts of all the
27 places the article is connected to. For bibliometric scholars, however, definitions of local
28 science must be theoretically grounded and operationalized into measurable variables.
29 Bibliometric scholars tend to measure local research based on the assumption that local and
30 international science differ in terms of their focus, the needs they address and their target
31 audience (e.g., Grančay et al., 2017; Gzoyan et al., 2023; Lopez-Piñero & Hicks, 2015;
32 Mongeon et al., 2022). Different bibliometric studies thus have different approaches to local
33 research. These approaches may relate to the indexing of journals in mainstream databases, the
34 location of the journal or its authors, the language of the publication, its topic, its explicit ties
35 to a particular local context, its intended audience, or its knowledge base. Arguably, some of
36 the approaches resemble more the “tangibles” (Chambers & Gillespie, 2000, p. 228) or
37 contextual factors manifested by localities than anything else. For example, publication in a
38 mainstream or non-mainstream journal can be viewed as an effect of locality, as the choice of
39 publication will be closely related to the relevant authors’ contexts. Thus, mainstream
40 indexation would not be a factor of locality but rather its consequence. From a constructivist
41 perspective, it could be argued that the effects of locality constitute meaningful practices which
42 reveal information about specific local contexts.

43 This study does not aim to propose a single definition of local research in bibliometric studies.
44 Instead, it explores how different definitions of local research can produce different citation
45 patterns when applied to the same analysis. In doing so, the importance of clarity, transparency,
46 and conceptual coherence in bibliometric research on local science is highlighted. To this end,
47 we adopt three of the most widely used approaches for conceptually defining local research in
48 bibliometric studies and operationalize them. This section outlines the conceptual foundations
49 of each approach, drawing on existing academic literature, and also examines their associated

1 citation patterns. For the conceptualization of local research, we draw on the framework
2 developed by Di Cesare and Robinson (2026), which frames such research according to three
3 dimensions: territory, producers, and recipients. The territory dimension encompasses research
4 linked to a particular location; the producers dimension refers to research built on local
5 expertise; and the recipients dimension encompasses research relevant to particular
6 communities. As the authors note, each dimension is not defined by a single element; rather,
7 several variables may serve as proxies. For instance, in the case of territory, these include
8 toponyms or language use; in the case of producers, they include the geographic concentration
9 of authors and references; and in the case of recipients, they include variables related to
10 visibility and use, such as database coverage and citations. While all three dimensions are
11 incorporated into this analysis, only one proxy per dimension is included. The following
12 subsections report the proxy selected for each dimension, its relevance, and the associated
13 citation patterns.

14

15 *2.1 Recipient dimension: database indexation*

16 2.1.1 Relevance in bibliometric research

17 The indexing of journals in different scholarly databases is often used to distinguish between
18 international and local knowledge production, with scholarly output being situated within
19 international, regional, and national circuits of knowledge (Beigel, 2014). International circuits
20 are defined by publications indexed in mainstream databases such as Scopus and Web of
21 Science (WoS), regional circuits by region-specific platforms such as SciELO, Latindex, or
22 African Journals Online (AJOL), and national circuits by locally published journals.
23 Publications in mainstream databases have become synonymous with ‘global science’ (Beigel,
24 2021), relegating journals outside them to ‘peripheral’ status (Salager-Meyer, 2015) and the
25 work published in them to the category of ‘local’ science (Guédon, 2011).

26 Classifying journals as international based on their indexing in Scopus or WoS takes for granted
27 the perceived objectivity of the selection criteria involved (Lillis & Curry, 2010). These
28 criteria—often presented as universal—have been criticised for perpetuating geographic,
29 linguistic, and disciplinary biases (Alonso-Álvarez, 2024; Chavarro et al., 2018) and for
30 codifying quality standards that privilege issues and styles that travel well in mainstream
31 circuits (Beigel, 2013, 2014; Beigel & Salatino, 2015). Despite this, mainstream databases
32 continue to be widely used to identify local journals in bibliometric analyses, often in
33 combination with other criteria such as language of publication (Milia et al., 2022; Milia &
34 Arvanitis, 2025; Tijssen, 2007; Sivertsen, 2016).

35 2.1.2 Associated citation patterns

36 Inclusion in mainstream databases significantly enhances a journal’s visibility and facilitates
37 dissemination to international audiences (Buela-Casal et al., 2006). Indexation in Scopus and
38 WoS has been consistently associated with higher citation counts (Chavarro et al., 2018).
39 Country-specific analyses corroborated this, showing that publications indexed in mainstream
40 sources tend to be cited more frequently by other indexed sources, as was found to be the case
41 for Croatia (Andreis & Jokić, 2008), Armenia (Gzoyan et al., 2023), Germany (Chi, 2014), and
42 South Africa (Tijssen, 2007). However, these studies rely solely on citations from indexed
43 sources, excluding citations from non-indexed sources, which may present a different picture.

44 Studies that include non-indexed sources suggest that alternative citation patterns emerge when
45 a broader scope is considered. Local journals often cover topics of high relevance to specific
46 research communities that are not addressed by indexed journals (Chavarro et al. 2017; Lopez-

1 Piñeiro & Hicks, 2015), and non-indexed papers tend to cite other non-indexed papers.
2 Moreover, publications not indexed in mainstream databases are primarily cited by domestic
3 audiences, as shown in Brazilian (Mugnaini et al., 2007), Armenian (Gzoyan et al., 2023), and
4 Malaysian contexts (Abrizah et al., 2013). These findings suggest that analyses relying solely
5 on mainstream databases overlook a substantial portion of the citation landscape and may
6 underestimate the visibility, relevance, and scholarly impact of local research.

8 *2.2 Territory dimension: toponym-based approaches*

9 2.2.1 Relevance in bibliometric research

10 Methods grounded in toponym-based analysis assume that locally focused research is
11 inherently tied to particular geographic contexts and therefore rely on the presence of toponyms
12 (place names) or demonyms (nationality names) in abstracts and titles to identify local research
13 (Chavarro et al., 2014; Sommer, 1990). Studies implementing this approach typically focus on
14 a specific country or geographic area that serves as the setting, territorial scope, or sociocultural
15 and political backdrop of the research. A toponym-based approach can be used to identify local
16 research at both the journal and publication levels.

17 At the journal level, bibliometric scholarship often assumes that work published in nationally
18 oriented journals engages with issues of domestic relevance. Journals often embody scientific
19 communities with shared topical, contextual, or methodological interests (Dawson & Topham,
20 2020; Granados, 2012; Pita González, 2016; Zuluaga Quintero, 2020), and since journal titles
21 typically reflect thematic and geographic scope, the presence of a country name may indicate a
22 deliberate focus on locally contextualized research (Jamali, 2024). Journal titles have
23 accordingly been used to identify local research in bibliometric analyses (Abrizah et al., 2013),
24 and this presumed link is further reflected in the trend toward de-nationalizing journal titles as
25 a strategy to enhance international visibility (Khelfaoui & Gingras, 2025).

26 At the publication level, authors in the Global South are more likely to geo-contextualize their
27 research than those in the Global North (Mongeon et al., 2022), which not only confines their
28 work to local relevance (Castro-Torres & Alburez-Gutiérrez, 2022) but also reinforces Northern
29 scientific dominance by positioning it as the seat of universal knowledge (Mignolo, 2018).
30 Despite this limitation, bibliometric applications of this approach include regional studies on
31 Latin America and the Caribbean (Arias & González, 2021; Miguel et al., 2024), sub-Saharan
32 Africa (Hedt-Gauthier et al., 2019), and national analyses of Canadian (Larivière, 2014),
33 Colombian (Ordóñez-Matamoros et al., 2010), and South African local research (Wright et al.,
34 2017).

35 2.2.2 Associated citation patterns

36 Although the citation patterns associated with geo-localized journal titles remain understudied,
37 journals including a country name in their title are often perceived as having a local focus and,
38 in some cases, as being of lower quality (Jamali, 2024). Many journals have responded to this
39 perception by removing country references from their titles and switching to English, a strategy
40 associated with increased citation rates and greater internationalization (Khelfaoui & Gingras,
41 2025).

42 At the publication level, geo-contextualized articles have generally been linked to a citation
43 disadvantage (Burns & Islam, 2024; Kahalon et al., 2022), though findings are mixed. For a
44 limited number of research areas related to health, environmental sciences, and geosciences,
45 geo-contextualized publications have been found to have higher citation counts (Abramo et al.,
46 2016), and recent comparative research has also revealed that, in certain fields, geo-

1 contextualized publications from the Global South have a higher average impact than non-geo-
2 contextualized publications (Mongeon et al., 2022). A possible explanation is that articles with
3 country names in their titles may benefit from a within-country citation advantage (Burns
4 &Islam, 2024).

6 *2.3 Producer dimension: author-based approaches*

7 2.3.1 Relevance in bibliometric research

8 Another common approach to locality considers the affiliations of the key actors in the
9 publication process, which are the authors. Author affiliation is a widely used indicator of both
10 research internationality and collaboration (Buela-Casal et al., 2006). This approach has been
11 applied in studies that examine locality across various contexts (Grančay et al., 2017; Moed et
12 al., 2020). In particular, it has been used to study the relevance of local African scientific
13 production in the global scientific landscape (Tijssen et al., 2006; Tijssen, 2007). It has also
14 been used to analyze the geographic distribution of certain areas of research (Boshoff et al.,
15 2024a), and the visibility of research from specific countries (e.g., Boshoff et al. 2024b on the
16 invisibility of Tanzanian forest science), and also used jointly with other approaches, such as
17 toponym approaches (Hedt-Gauthier et al., 2019).

18 2.3.2 Associated citation patterns

19 International collaboration has been consistently associated with higher citation impact
20 (Didegah & Thelwall, 2013; Kwiek, 2021). In general, publications with international co-
21 authors tend to be cited more frequently than those with authors from the same country only.
22 Prior research has also suggested that the higher impact of internationally co-authored work
23 may be linked to the variety of topics it covers (Vélez-Estevez et al., 2022). Bibliometric studies
24 focusing on sub-Saharan Africa, using WoS-indexed publications, report similar findings:
25 internationally co-authored articles receive more citations, with the strongest advantage
26 observed in international collaborations involving non-African partners (Onyancha, 2020;
27 Sooryamoorthy, 2017).

28 National citation bias and country self-citations are also well-documented in the bibliometric
29 literature (Baccini & Petrovich, 2023; Pasterkamp et al., 2007; Wang et al., 2024). Publications
30 tend to have higher impact in their immediate environments, resulting in more citations from
31 national colleagues (Lancho Barrantes et al., 2012; Abramo et al., 2021). This pattern is more
32 pronounced in the social sciences and humanities than in the natural sciences and engineering.
33 It is also stronger in publications with exclusively domestic authorship (Khelfaoui et al., 2020).

35 **3. Data and methods**

36 *3.1 Approaches to operationalizing local research*

37 The operationalization of the different approaches towards local research is presented in Table
38 1. For the database indexing-based approach, a publication was considered local when it
39 appeared in a journal not indexed in either Scopus or WoS. This study adopted two toponym-
40 based approaches. At the journal level, a publication was considered local if it appeared in a
41 journal whose title included the name of the country in which it is published. For instance, the
42 *South African Journal of Science* is published in South Africa, and its title includes the country
43 name. At the document level, a publication was considered local if the title of the article
44 included the name of the country that publishes the journal. For this analysis, only toponyms of
45 countries were considered. Subnational names—such as those of regions, provinces, or cities—

1 are excluded. Consequently, publications that refer solely to subnational units without explicitly
 2 naming the country were not classified as local. Finally, the author-based approaches presented
 3 here considered a publication to be local if all or at least one of the authors were affiliated with
 4 an institution in the country that publishes the journal. The operationalization used here is more
 5 restrictive than most common standard bibliometric practices and other recent approaches (e.g.,
 6 Di Césare & Robinson, 2026). Except in the database indexing-based approach—where it is
 7 not feasible—it requires that articles or journals be not only geo-contextualized or authored by
 8 researchers from a single country, but also that this country match the journal's country of
 9 origin. This dual requirement is intended to prevent or minimize the misclassification of
 10 literature with a strong international component as local. For example, a publication written by
 11 Tanzanian authors using a South African case study and published in the *Nigerian Journal of*
 12 *Clinical Practice* would not qualify as local literature under this definition, yet would be
 13 classified as such by three criteria in less restrictive approaches. Similar, more restrictive,
 14 approaches have been used in previous literature to identify local research (Mongeon et al.,
 15 2022).

16
17

Table 1. Operationalization of local approaches

Approach	Criteria	Definition
Database indexing-based approach	Journal in WoS/Scopus	A publication is considered local when it appears in a journal that is not indexed in WoS or Scopus.
Toponym-based approach	Journal title	A publication is considered local if it appears in a journal whose title includes the name of the country in which it is published.
	Article title	A publication is considered local if the title of the article includes the name of the journal's country
Author-based approach	All authors	All the authors are affiliated with an institution in the same country as the journal
	Any author	At least one author is affiliated with an institution in the same country as the journal

18

19 3.2 Data

20 The analysis relied on four sources of data, two of which were key for most of the analyses:

- 21 • African Journals Online (AJOL): Journal data retrieved from the AJOL website in
22 February 2024 using the R library *rvest* (Wickham, 2025).
- 23 • OpenAlex: Publication and journal data retrieved from the CWTS in-house version of
24 OpenAlex, updated until August 2024.

25 The metadata of publications in AJOL journals published between 2016 and 2018 were
 26 extracted from OpenAlex. Only publications from AJOL journals in OpenAlex were selected,
 27 and not also other African publications in OpenAlex, to ensure that all items in the dataset are
 28 peer-reviewed journal articles, thus meeting a minimum shared quality standard. This was done
 29 because peer review cannot necessarily be assumed for all publications classified as articles in
 30 OpenAlex. Although AJOL journals are supposedly African based, not all of them were located

1 in Africa according to OpenAlex. As different data sources might employ different criteria to
 2 assign the country of a journal, only journals classified as located in African countries in both
 3 data sources were kept. Therefore, we filtered out articles from journals not classified as African
 4 by OpenAlex to ensure data consistency. Table 2 shows the number of publications and unique
 5 number of journals during each step of the publication selection process. The final set of AJOL
 6 publications —AJOL in OpenAlex by ISSN matching (2016-2018, restricted to African-based
 7 journals)— was the one used in the analysis. Finally, publications citing the AJOL publications
 8 within a five-year window were also retrieved, as indicated in Table 2. Tables S1, S2 and S3 in
 9 the Supplemental Materials show the number of documents per country, research area and
 10 locality type.

11

12 Table 2. Number of publications and unique journals during each step of the publication
 13 selection process.

Stepwise publication sets	# publications	# journals
Step 1: AJOL in OpenAlex by ISSN matching (all years)	304,407	571
Step 2: AJOL in OpenAlex by ISSN matching (2016-2018)	45,554	389
Step 3: AJOL in OpenAlex by ISSN matching (2016-2018, restricted to African-based journals)	42,092	373
AJOL publications in Step 3 that have been cited	24,933	354
Publications citing the AJOL publications in Step 3 (5 years citation window)	121,003	20,380

14

15 AJOL publications were classified according to OpenAlex’s domains (social sciences, life
 16 sciences, health sciences, and physical sciences). Additional metadata was retrieved from
 17 OpenAlex, including publication year, title, authors’ affiliation country, and the journal’s
 18 country. These were used in executing the author-based and toponym-based approaches to
 19 locality. The *GeoNames*¹ database was used to extract toponyms from article and journal titles.

20 Two other data sources were used for the database indexing-based approach to locality:

- 21 • WoS: The CWTS in-house version of WoS, updated until September 2024, which
 22 includes the Science Citation Index Expanded (SCIE), the Social Sciences Citation
 23 Index (SSCI), the Arts & Humanities Citation Index (AHCI), and the Emerging Sources
 24 Citation Index (ESCI).
- 25 • Scopus: The CWTS in-house version of Scopus, updated in March 2024.

26

¹ <http://www.geonames.org>. Only entities with PLCI feature codes (<http://www.geonames.org/export/codes.html>) and their demonyms were used.

1 3.3 Statistical analyses

2 In terms of analysis, we first created profiles of the countries and research areas in our dataset,
3 as well as presenting the distribution of local versus non-local publications and citations
4 according to the five locality criteria. We then calculated the correlation between the five
5 criteria. For each locality criterion, we computed three sets of summary statistics—the average
6 number of citations per paper, the average time (in years) to the first citation, and the percentage
7 of publications with zero citations.

8 To explore the profile of publications citing local literature according to their locality status and
9 geographic origin, we calculated two indicators for each locality criterion. First, we examined
10 the locality status (local or non-local) of the citing publications to determine whether local
11 literature tends to be cited more frequently by other local publications. Second, we assessed the
12 international scope of the citations—that is, whether citations to local literature originate from
13 the same country as the cited publications or from other countries. This allowed us to trace the
14 citation flows and identify regional or international audiences engaging with local research.

15 All analyses employed a variation of the same metric: an adjusted share of citations. We used
16 an adjusted metric rather than a simple proportion to account for structural imbalances in the
17 dataset (see Table S3). A simple proportion—such as the share of local citations within a
18 specific research area—may conflate actual citation behavior with disparities in the volume of
19 local versus non-local publications. Given that non-local publications are often more numerous,
20 direct comparisons can be misleading. To address this, we normalized the data by dividing the
21 observed local share in a given research area by the expected share across all areas for the same
22 locality type. This adjusted share reflects whether local publications are over- or under-cited
23 relative to their availability, thus enabling fairer comparisons across research areas and locality
24 criteria.

25 To ensure robustness, we applied a minimum threshold of 10 publications per combination of
26 research area, locality type, and citation status (local vs. non-local). In all cases, the research
27 area refers to that of the cited publication.

28 The adjusted share of citations was calculated in two ways. In the first calculation, it was
29 defined as the ratio of the observed share of citations from local publications within a given
30 research area to the expected share of citations from local publications based on the overall
31 distribution of citations across all research areas. Specifically, it was defined as the proportion
32 of citations from local publications in a given area divided by the total citations in that area,
33 normalized by the proportion of all citations from local publications (across areas) within a
34 given locality criterion relative to the total citations under that same criterion. Thus, if a denotes
35 the cited publication research area, the adjusted share of citations is defined by the following
36 equation:

37 Equation 1. Adjusted share of citations based on locality status of citing publications

$$38 \quad \text{Adjusted share of citations} \\ \text{from local publications in area } a = \frac{\frac{\text{Citations from local publications in area } a}{\text{Total citations in area } a}}{\frac{\text{Total citations from local publications in all areas}}{\text{Total citations in all areas}}}$$

39 Thus, an adjusted share below 1 indicates that citations from local publications are less frequent
40 than expected in a given research area, suggesting an underrepresentation relative to their
41 overall availability. Conversely, an adjusted share above 1 implies that citations from local
42 publications are more frequent than expected, indicating a relative interest from local literature
43 in that area.

1 For the second calculation, we applied the same normalization procedure to assess whether
 2 citations originate from the same country as the cited publications or from a different country.
 3 In this case, the adjusted share compares the observed proportion of same-country citations
 4 within each research area to the expected proportion based on the overall distribution of same-
 5 and different-country citations within each locality type. This allows us to evaluate whether
 6 citations from domestic sources are over- or underrepresented relative to their general
 7 occurrence in the dataset. Thus, if a denotes the cited publication research area, the adjusted
 8 share of citations is defined by the following equation:

9 Equation 2. Adjusted share of citations based on same-country status of citing publications

$$10 \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{Adjusted share of citations} \\ \text{from publications} \\ \text{from the same country in area } a \end{array} = \frac{\frac{\text{Citations from same country publications in area } a}{\text{Total citations in area } a}}{\frac{\text{Total citations from same country publications in all areas}}{\text{Total citations in all areas}}}$$

11 As in the previous calculation, an adjusted share below 1 indicates that citations from same-
 12 country publications are less frequent than expected in a given research area, whereas an
 13 adjusted share above 1 implies that citations from same-country publications are more frequent
 14 than in the overall dataset.

15 All the visualizations in the article were created using *ggplot2* (Wickham, 2016).

16

17 4. Results and discussion

18 4.1 Correlation between locality criteria

19 Figure 1 presents the correlations between the different criteria of locality. The graph shows
 20 that the locality criteria are not strongly correlated with one another. *Journal in WoS/Scopus*
 21 has a low negative correlation with *Journal title* and almost zero correlations with the rest of
 22 the locality criteria. Although *Journal title*, *Article title*, *All authors* and *Any author* positively
 23 correlate with one another, their correlation coefficients are very low. The exception is the
 24 correlation between *All authors* and *Any author*, which is expected because the *All author*
 25 publications are a subset of the *Any author* publications.

26

Figure 1: Correlation of locality criteria

27

1 The low correlation values are not completely unexpected, as previous analyses using different
 2 locality criteria have yielded similar results. For example, at the journal level, Di Césare and
 3 Robinson-García (2026) demonstrated that, depending on the chosen criterion, journals
 4 classified as local according to one definition are often not classified as such by other criteria.
 5 While some degree of overlap exists, their study highlights that the interaction between different
 6 locality approaches is generally limited.

7 *4.2 Citation statistics by research area*

8 Figure 2 shows the percentage of publications with zero citations across the five criteria of local
 9 research. It compares each percentage to the corresponding percentage for non-local research,
 10 also disaggregating them by research field. The grey horizontal lines indicate OpenAlex’s
 11 broader domain classification. In order, the first group belongs to the Social Sciences domain,
 12 the second group to Health Sciences, the third to Life Sciences and the last one to Physical
 13 Sciences. The *Journal in WoS/Scopus* criterion reveals the largest disparities, with local
 14 publications exhibiting a higher proportion of uncited outputs in most fields. For the remaining
 15 criteria, the differences between local and non-local publications are more modest. Under both
 16 toponym-based criteria, local publications generally show a lower share of uncited papers,
 17 particularly in the social sciences and selected areas of the physical sciences. In contrast, within
 18 the health and life sciences, the proportion of uncited publications is similar for both local and
 19 non-local outputs. For the author-based criteria, non-local publications tend to have a slightly
 20 lower percentage of uncited articles, especially in the life and health sciences.

21 Figure 2: Percentage of publications with zero citations by locality criterion
 22 and research area

23
 24 Figure 3 shows the average number of citations per paper for the five locality criteria,
 25 comparing each citation average to the same for non-local research. The plots reveal that the
 26 relationship between citation impact and locality varies depending on both the definition of
 27 local research and the research area. Under the *Journal in WoS/Scopus* criterion, non-local
 28 research consistently receives more citations on average than local research across all fields.
 29 However, this difference is relatively small in certain physical sciences fields, such as energy,
 30 engineering, and physics and astronomy. A similar pattern emerges under the *All authors*
 31 criterion, although the average citation gap between local and non-local publications is is

1 narrower—particularly in some areas of the social sciences. Notably, in fields such as decision
 2 sciences and chemical engineering, local research exhibits higher citation averages than non-
 3 local research. Under the *Any author* criterion, local research shows slightly higher average
 4 citations in the social sciences and in some physical science fields, while receiving fewer
 5 citations in the health and life sciences. When applying the *Journal title* criterion, local research
 6 generally receives more citations on average than non-local research across all domains, with
 7 smaller differences observed in the health sciences. Finally, under the *Article title* criterion,
 8 local research tends to receive more citations in all social science fields and in several areas
 9 across other domains.

10 Figure 3: Average citations per paper by locality criterion and research area

11
 12 Finally, Figure 4 presents the average number of years to the first citation, by locality criterion
 13 and research area. The graphs show that for most criteria —*Journal title*, *Article title*, *All*
 14 *authors*, and *Any author*— there are no significant differences between local and non-local
 15 research. However, under the *Journal in WoS/Scopus* criterion, local publications experience a

1 longer delay, with the average time to first citation being between six months and one year
 2 greater than for non-local publications.

3 Figure 4: Average years until first citation by locality criterion and research area

4
 5 The results indicate that local publications cited and used at levels comparable to non-local
 6 publications across most definitions of locality. This highlights the significance of local
 7 academic research within the broader scientific landscape. While non-local literature tends to
 8 show slightly better performance for most indicators and locality criteria, the most notable
 9 differences appear under the *Journal in WoS/Scopus* criterion. For other locality criteria, the
 10 performance gap is smaller and varies depending on the research area. In particular, under the
 11 *Any author* criterion, local research outperforms non-local research in certain fields. However,
 12 this outcome is not unexpected, as this criterion includes internationally co-authored
 13 publications—as it requires only one author to be affiliated with an institution in the journal’s
 14 country—which may enhance citation impact.

15 Regarding the *Journal title* and *Article title* criteria, the findings diverge somewhat from the
 16 literature that suggests a citation disadvantage for geo-contextualized research. Prior analyses
 17 of local academic output have typically relied on WoS or Scopus data, which are known to
 18 underrepresent research from the Global South, which might affect the results. Using
 19 OpenAlex, Mongeon and colleagues (Mongeon et al., 2022) reported that in certain research
 20 areas, geo-contextualized and local research from the Global South received, on average, more
 21 citations than non-local or non-geo-contextualized publications. The findings presented here
 22 partially support that conclusion. However, a deeper analysis is required to fully assess the
 23 citation impact of geo-contextualized research in the Global South.

24 *4.3 Profile of publications citing local research*

25 As previous literature has noted (e.g., Gzoyan, 2023; Mugnaini et al., 2007), local academic
 26 publications often reach different audiences compared to non-local publications. This section
 27 examines the profile of publications citing local research in Africa to explore these dynamics
 28 further. Specifically, it analyzes citation sources based on two classifications of the citing
 29 publications: (1) local and non-local citing publications, using the same criteria applied to the
 30 cited publications—citations are considered local if they come from publications classified as
 31 local, regardless of their country of origin; and (2) same-country versus different-country

1 citations, based on the affiliation of the citing authors. This dual classification enables us to
 2 assess whether local academic literature circulates primarily within local or international
 3 scholarly networks and to what extent it holds relevance for countries beyond the one in which
 4 it was published.

5 Figure 5 presents the adjusted share of citations from local publications to both local and non-
 6 local articles. Overall, the graph indicates that differences in citation patterns are more strongly
 7 associated with the research area than with the local or non-local status of the publication. For
 8 example, publications in the arts and humanities tend to receive more citations from local
 9 sources, whereas those in materials science are more frequently cited by non-local publications.

10 Among the classification types, the *Article title* criterion reveals the sharpest contrast between
 11 local and non-local citation patterns. Figure 5 highlights the varying citation dynamics of geo-
 12 contextualized local research across disciplines. In fields with a more local orientation—such
 13 as health and medical sciences—local publications tend to be cited more often by non-local
 14 publications. Conversely, in fields that are typically less locally focused, such as mathematics
 15 or materials science, local publications are predominantly cited by other local publications.

16 Figure 5. Adjusted share of citations from local publications – reported for five locality
 17 criteria (each with two subcategories, local and non-local), broken down by research area

18
 19

20 Figure 6 illustrates the adjusted share of citations originating from publications affiliated with
 21 the same country as the cited work versus those from other countries. As in the previous figure,
 22 the most notable variations are observed across research areas. Fields such as arts and
 23 humanities and social sciences exhibit a higher proportion of citations from within the same
 24 country, reflecting their stronger local orientation.

25 Figure 6. Adjusted share of citations from publications from the same country – reported for
 26 five locality criteria (each with two subcategories, local and non-local), broken down by
 27 research area

1
2 When considered alongside the preceding figure, several nuanced patterns emerge. For
3 example, in nursing, citations stem from both local and non-local publications, but primarily
4 from publications affiliated with other countries. This suggests that nursing publications are
5 equally ‘used’ in local and non-local research, but they have a more international reach. In
6 contrast, earth and planetary sciences receive most of their citations from non-local
7 publications, yet these often originate from the same country. This pattern implies that local
8 knowledge is disseminated through publications with a geographic link but an international
9 scope—i.e., studies published in international circuits, studies with a broader international
10 focus, or in research with international collaborations.

11
12 **5. Conclusion**

13 The analysis shows that local and non-local citation distributions depend heavily on the
14 definition of ‘local research’ used. For example, differences in citations between local and non-
15 local articles are more pronounced when the database indexing criterion is used, but less so with
16 the other definitions. These results confirm that different definitions and operationalizations of
17 local research yield substantially different analytical outcomes. It is therefore important to make
18 informed decisions about what is considered local, as well as to reflect on the meaning and
19 implications of each definition.

20 In terms of citation performance, the results indicate that local publications are cited at levels
21 comparable to non-local publications across most definitions of locality. The notable exception
22 is the WoS/Scopus indexing criterion, under which publications deemed ‘local’ have lower
23 citation rates. These findings partially align with previous research (Mongeon et al., 2022), yet
24 some observed patterns call for deeper investigation in future analysis. Importantly, this study
25 aimed to present a novel approach by combining multiple definitions of local research with data
26 sources that extend beyond mainstream databases as incorporating publications not indexed in
27 WoS or Scopus is particularly relevant for underrepresented regions such as Africa. However,
28 expanding the dataset may also lead to new findings that diverge from previous academic
29 literature, highlighting the need to revisit and refine existing assumptions about the visibility
30 and impact of local research. Regarding dissemination scope, the findings suggest that local
31 research holds relevance not only for domestic audiences but also for international scholarly
32 communities. Local publications receive citations from both within and beyond the publishing

1 country, challenging assumptions of their limited reach. The use of different locality definitions
2 reveals distinct patterns of scholarly communication shaped by disciplinary contexts.

3 These findings are consistent with the framework of Di Césare and Robinson (2026), on which
4 this study was based, as the dimensions of territory, producers, and recipients capture different
5 aspects of locality. The differences in citation patterns across the various definitions further
6 support this, as each definition appears to attract a different pattern of citations. The results also
7 emphasize the need for nuanced, context-aware approaches in the assessment of local research,
8 especially when designing policies or evaluation frameworks aimed at recognizing the diverse
9 contributions of scholarly work rooted in specific geographic or social settings

10 The particular limitations of the database-indexing approach deserve attention, both in terms of
11 its conceptual ambiguity and its practical implications. Framing research that is not included in
12 mainstream databases as local does not correspond to any meaningful link to a particular
13 locality. The closest locality-related justification would be the assumption that mainstream
14 science is directed at a global community while non-mainstream science is directed at local
15 audiences. However, this would imply accepting that commercial companies, rather than
16 scientists and scientific communities, have the legitimacy to determine what is of global interest
17 and what remains local. This is also problematic in a practical and political sense, given the
18 well-documented biases in these data sources (Alonso-Álvarez, 2024; Asubiaro et al., 2024).
19 Furthermore, compared to other definitions, which yield more nuanced results, the database-
20 indexing approach shows a clear tendency to associate local research with lower citation rates.
21 Generalizing this finding without explicitly defining what is meant by ‘local’ risks understating
22 the use and relevance of local research.

23 It is worth noting, however, that the framework employed here does not address the deeper
24 conceptual meanings of the locality dimensions used. Consequently, neither does this study. Di
25 Césare and Robinson (2026) offer a practical account of how local research has been
26 operationalized in bibliometric studies, organizing existing approaches around three
27 dimensions. However, their framework departs from practical usage rather than from the
28 conceptualizations developed by sociologists of science. As discussed above, if all research is
29 locally situated (Harding, 1997; Mignolo, 2018; Turnbull, 1993; Turnbull, 1997), it remains an
30 open question as to which locality factors each of these dimensions actually captures. What, for
31 instance, do the intention and capacity to publish in a mainstream journal, to write in English,
32 or to recontextualize research, reveal about the particular locality contexts in which that
33 research is produced? Beyond some recent and notable exceptions (Sunagawa et al., 2026),
34 these questions remain largely unexplored.

35 This analysis has several limitations. First, the matching between databases was performed at
36 the journal level, meaning that if a journal was indexed in a given database, all articles published
37 in that journal were considered included. While this approach helps avoid matching errors due
38 to incomplete or incorrect metadata, it may result in the inclusion of articles that are not actually
39 indexed—for example, in the case of Scopus or WoS, although a journal is indexed in the
40 database, the database may not cover issues prior to inclusion. Other limitations relate to the
41 toponym-based approach. The analysis employed here relies solely on country names, rather
42 than regional or city-level designations. While more inclusive approaches might capture
43 additional publications, existing sub-country toponym lists can introduce noise — for instance,
44 the entries for South Africa in GeoNames (the database used here) include “North West”, a
45 term that authors may use to indicate coordinates or regions in other countries rather than the
46 specific South African province. Since it is not feasible to curate the full GeoNames database
47 for all African countries, this approach adopts country-level toponyms as a conservative
48 measure. Additionally, toponym-based approaches may reproduce biases in how place names
49 are used across countries. This issue has been studied primarily in comparisons between the

1 Global North and the Global South (e.g., Mongeon et al., 2022); however, the authors have not
2 found comparable studies in the African context.

3 Another limitation concerns the availability of metadata in OpenAlex, particularly reference
4 lists. The descriptives (see Table S3) show that 84% of citing articles are indexed in either
5 Scopus or WoS. This high coverage by mainstream databases is surprising, as OpenAlex is a
6 more comprehensive source (Culbert et al., 2024). This number, along with findings from
7 previous research (Alonso-Álvarez & van Eck, 2024), suggests that the references of non-
8 Scopus/WoS-indexed articles are more likely to be missing in OpenAlex and therefore cannot
9 be identified using OpenAlex reference lists. Further research might explore the use of
10 additional data sources, such as the full text of the articles, to address this limitation.

11 Overall, this study reinforces the idea that the results of bibliometric analyses of local research
12 depend heavily on the definition used. Since the conceptualization and operationalization of
13 local research evidently influence the observed citation patterns of African publications, it is
14 essential that researchers studying these publications clearly define their object of study and
15 their approach. This should include an explanation of the rationale behind these choices and an
16 explicit acknowledgement of the limitations of the research. Also, as local science continues to
17 be a theoretically contested concept, reflexivity in its use is advised. Failing to do so risks
18 reproducing the systemic structures that shape how science is produced and published. For
19 instance, if research from the Global South is largely absent from mainstream data sources,
20 studies that adopt this definition of local may inadvertently equate local with Global South.
21 Overlooking the realities and constraints underlying academic publishing systems can obscure
22 structural conditions, making them appear as isolated cases of impact, quality, or relevance
23 rather than reflections of broader economic, social, historical, and colonial inequalities.

24

25 **Open science practices**

26 The OpenAlex data (obtained from the OpenAlex snapshot) and AJOL data (retrieved from the
27 AJOL website) used in this paper is openly available (a structured version of the AJOL data used
28 in this paper can be found here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15383374>). This is not the case
29 for the data obtained from the Scopus and WoS databases. Due to license restrictions, we are
30 not allowed to redistribute Scopus and WoS data and the data used in this paper can therefore
31 not be made available.

32

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Author contributions

Alonso-Álvarez: Conceptualization; Data curation; Investigation; Formal Analysis; Funding acquisition; Methodology; Visualization; Writing – original draft.
Boshoff: Conceptualization; Methodology; Writing – review & editing.

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